

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of 2-Methylpiperazinedithiocarbamate Complexes with some First Row Transition Metals

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New complexes of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 2-methylpiperazinedithiocarbamate (2-Mepipzdtc) have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analyses magnetic, ir, electronic and esr spectral data. The ligand exhibits bidentate nature and the complexes are soluble only in strongly coordinating and highly polar solvents like DMF and DMSO. From the esr spectral data of copper(II) derivative the bonding parameters (σ^2 , β_1^2 and β_2^2) have been calculated and which indicate strong metal-ligand covalency.

SYNTHESIS of metal dithiocarbamates and their characterisation have been a subject of extensive investigation¹⁻³. Besides having their wide and established applications⁴, they show some interesting structure-reactivity relationship⁵. Fe^{III}-dithiocarbamates are the earliest examples showing the effect N-substituents on low-spin $\rightleftharpoons$ high-spin crossover phenomena⁶. In this communication, we report the synthesis and characterisation of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} dithiocarbamates with heterocyclic substituent 2-methylpiperazine. As the nature

where, $n=2$, $M=Co, Ni$ and Cu , and $n=3$, $M=Cr$ and Fe .

of the substituents influence the C-N and C-S bond order and subsequent donor behaviour of the sulphur atoms, it was of interest to evaluate the spectral and magnetic parameters and compare them with the other dithiocarbamates.

Experimental

The sodium salt of 2-methylpiperazinedithiocarbamate (2-Mepipzdtc Na) was prepared and purified as reported earlier⁷.

Preparation of complexes: Cr(2-Mepipzdtc)₃—chromium(III) chloride hexahydrate and the sodium salt of the ligand (in 1 : 3 molar ratio) were refluxed in ethanol for 4 h. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Fe(2-Mepipzdtc)₃ was prepared by stirring freshly precipitated ferric hydroxide with equimolar amounts of 2-methylpiperazine and CS₂ dissolved in absolute ethanol⁸. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol, dried under reduced pressure and kept in

dark to prevent any photochemical reaction. Co(2-Mepipzdtc)₂—cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate and sodium salt of the ligand (in 1 : 2 molar ratio) in ethanol were stirred vigorously for 1 h. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Ni(2-Mepipzdtc)₂ and Cu(2-Mepipzdtc)₂ were prepared by similar procedure described for Co(2-Mepipzdtc)₂.

The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, low frequency ir spectra (KBr) on a Polytech FIR 30 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer using BaSO₄ as reference material and esr spectra of the powdered samples after dilution in a diamagnetic host, recorded at ~77 K on a Varian E-112 spectrometer (X-band) using TCNE ($g=2.00277$) as g -marker. Magnetic moment at room temperature was measured on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. C, H and N were determined by a Carlo-Erba 1106 instrument.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data are shown in Table 1. The compounds were found insoluble in common organic solvents and sparingly soluble in DMF, DMSO, dichloromethane and nitromethane.

The chromium(III) derivative had a magnetic moment of 4.1 B.M. in accordance with a ⁴A_{2g} ground state in an octahedral field. The solid state electronic spectrum showed bands at 16 150 and 22 300 cm⁻¹, assigned to ⁴A_{2g}→⁴T_{2g} and ⁴A_{2g}→⁴T_{1g}(F) transitions respectively. Making use of these transitions 10Dq, B and β values were calculated to be 16 150 cm⁻¹, 605 cm⁻¹ and 0.65 respectively. From esr spectrum the g_{iso} value was found to be 1.987±0.01 and the spin-orbit coupling constant λ was 31 cm⁻¹ from the relation $g=2.0023 [1-(4\lambda/10Dq)]$. The large reduction from the free-ion

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd	Colour	Decomp P temp °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	S	M
Cr(2-Mepipzdtc) ₂	Light grey	235	37.81 (37.41)	5.43 (5.71)	15.03 (14.54)	32.88 (33.31)	8.94 (9.00)
Fe(2-Mepipzdtc) ₂	Dark brown	245	37.28 (37.16)	5.36 (5.67)	14.32 (14.45)	33.22 (33.09)	9.21 (9.69)
Co(2-Mepipzdtc) ₂	Green	282	35.11 (35.19)	5.18 (5.37)	18.54 (18.68)	31.46 (31.34)	14.25 (14.40)
Ni(2-Mepipzdtc) ₂	Olive green	288	31.28 (31.35)	5.31 (5.38)	13.62 (13.70)	31.23 (31.35)	14.48 (14.35)
Cu(2-Mepipzdtc) ₂	Brown	265	34.59 (34.80)	5.25 (5.32)	13.42 (13.53)	31.12 (30.98)	15.42 (15.35)

value of 90 cm⁻¹ indicates high metal-ligand covalency. Compared to other dithio-system (such as dithiophosphates), the higher 10Dq value in the present case is due to higher C-S bond order in dithiocarbamates than the P-S bond order of dithiophosphate.

The room temperature magnetic moment of the iron(III) complex was 5.82 B.M. indicating high-spin nature of the complex. The ferric dithiocarbamate provides an interesting probe to observe high-spin ⇌ low-spin crossover with change in the strength of the ligand field and the nature of the substituent group. In strong ligand field, the lowest energy state of O_h symmetry is ²T_{2g} (t_{2g}⁵) with S=1/2 and favour a low-spin state showing a μ_{eff} value around 2.0 B.M. In presence of a weak ligand field the lowest energy state is ⁶A_{1g} (t_{2g}³e_g²) with S=5/2, favouring a high-spin state with a μ_{eff} value around 5.9 B.M. The thermal equilibrium between these two limiting case, S=1/2 ⇌ S=5/2 has been explained on the basis of structure and strength of the ligand field^{8,9}. This can be elucidated by the resonance forms I and II.

Form I represents a complex with a secondary amine substituent of low basicity, due to which the C-N bond order is reduced and Fe-S bond order increases (because of back-donation of electrons from metal to ligand) with subsequent shortening of Fe-S bond. This enhanced covalency strengthens the ligand field and favours a low-spin state. From X-ray and Mössbauer studies it is observed that μ_{eff} decreases with the shortening of mean Fe-S distance^{10,11}. Form II represents ligands having substituent with more basic nitrogen lone-pair, resulting a shift of electron density towards C-S bond which will enhance ionic radius of sulphur and lengthen the Fe-S bond due to increased π-antibonding effect. This causes a diminished separation of t_{2g} and e_g orbitals favouring a high-spin state. The high-spin nature of the present complex is com-

parable to those observed for pyrrolidine and morpholinyl derivatives⁹. The electronic spectrum of the solid compound showed bands around 5 800, 16 130, 19 200sh, 29 200 and 37 800 cm⁻¹. The band at 5 800 cm⁻¹ could be due to superimposition of ⁴T₁ → ⁶A₁ and ⁴F₁ → ²T₂ transitions and those observed around 29 200 and 37 800 cm⁻¹ may be due to L→M or M→L charge transfer and π→π* transitions, respectively. The esr spectrum of the solid at liquid nitrogen temperature showed three g-values (g₁=2.98, g₂=2.44 and g₃=2.01) and are indicative of trigonally distorted octahedral structure.

The cobalt(II) derivative had a magnetic moment of 2.28 B.M. suggesting low-spin species. The esr spectrum was anisotropic with three g-values (g₁=2.27, g₂=2.05 and g₃=2.01) similar to those found for other CoS₄ systems^{1,12} and indicate a tetragonally distorted square-planar geometry. The electronic spectrum of the solid showed bands around 15 150, 20 600sh, 25 300, 29 800 and 38 100 cm⁻¹ and the first three were assigned to ²A_{1g} → ²B_{2g}, → ²E_g and → ²B_{1g} transitions respectively. The higher energy bands observed at 29 800 and 38 100 cm⁻¹ could be assigned to L→M charge transfer or π→π* and π→π* transitions, respectively.

The diamagnetic nature and the spectral features of the nickel(II) derivative are suggestive of square-planar structure with NiS₄ moiety. The reflectance spectrum and solution spectrum in dichloromethane showed band in almost similar positions indicating the retention of the structure in solution. The band observed at 15 870, 20 400 and 23 800sh cm⁻¹ were assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, → ¹B_{1g} and → ¹E_g transitions, respectively. The 10Dq value was calculated from in-plane d_{x²-y²} → d_{xy} transition by using the relation, ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} (d_{x²-y²} → d_{xy}) = 10Dq - 35F₄ (F₄ = 80 cm⁻¹) and was 18 550 cm⁻¹.

The copper(II) derivative had a magnetic moment of 1.76 B.M. The electronic spectrum in the solid state showed bands at 15 150, 21 700, 33 300 and 40 600 cm⁻¹ and were assigned as ³B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} (d_{x²-y²} → d_{xy}), ²B_{1g} → ²E_g (d_{xz}; d_{yz} → d_{x²-y²}), metal-ligand charge transfer and π→π* transitions in a D_{2h} (very nearly D_{4h}) symmetry. The esr spectrum of the diluted powder (doped in 1 : 100 zinc matrix) was recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature and was

axial in nature (figure not shown). The spin hamiltonian parameters were found to be $g_{\parallel}=2.062$, $g_{\perp}=2.021$, $A_{\parallel}=150$ G and $A_{\perp}=26$ G. The observed esr spectral and magnetic data fitted well to the relation, $\mu_{\text{eff}} \approx 1/3(g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp}) \sqrt{S(S+1)}$, which was 1.762 B.M. (observed 1.76). The bonding parameters, α^2 , β_1^2 and β^2 representing in-plane σ -bonding, in-plane π -bonding and out-of-plane π -bonding respectively, were evaluated by using the values of $g_{\parallel}$, $g_{\perp}$ and electronic spectral data adopting the equations as defined by Kivelson and Neiman¹³ and were found to be 0.512, 0.65 and 0.593, respectively. From these values it is observed that the metal-ligand bond is quite covalent particularly the smaller value of β_1^2 compared to other dithiocarbamates with alkyl substituent might be indicative of the considerable in-plane π -bonding in heterocyclic substituted dithiocarbamate.

In the ir spectra of the complexes, the strong band observed around 1440 cm^{-1} was assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ which lies intermediate between $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ indicating a partial double bond character in the C-N bond. Alongwith this a single band was observed in the range $950-965 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_{\text{C=S}}$). The results are indicative of the bidentate nature of the ligand¹⁴. The ($\nu_{\text{CS}} + \delta_{\text{SCS}}$) and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ vibrations were found around 535 cm^{-1} and $340-380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

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